

D2.5 Recycling and ecodesign guidelines

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Executive summary

In this report a roadmap that addresses the environmental hotspots of car batteries is shown. Materials and processes with the greatest environmental impacts are identified and the consequent general eco-design strategies aligned to decrease these environmental carriers are described for each of the stages analysed: Production (materials and chemistry), Use (charging system, thermal management-BMS, driving cycle), and End of life (2nd Eol, final EoL). Having into account all of them, a conceptualized battery design based in both technical and environmental dimensions with specific actions to be deployed along the project and special emphasis in recycling options is included.

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List of abbreviations

<i>BEV</i>	<i>Battery Electric vehicle</i>
<i>BMS</i>	<i>Battery Management System</i>
<i>CE</i>	<i>Circular Economy</i>
<i>CRMs</i>	<i>Critical Raw Materials</i>
<i>DfA</i>	<i>Design for Assembly</i>
<i>DfM</i>	<i>Design for Modularity</i>
<i>EOL</i>	<i>End-of-Life</i>
<i>EV</i>	<i>Electric Vehicle</i>
<i>FEA</i>	<i>Finite Element Analysis</i>
<i>GHG</i>	<i>Greenhouse Gas</i>
<i>GWP</i>	<i>Global Warming Potential</i>
<i>HEV</i>	<i>Hybrid electric vehicle</i>
<i>ISO</i>	<i>International Organization for Standardization</i>
<i>LCA</i>	<i>Life Cycle Assessment</i>
<i>LFP</i>	<i>Lithium iron Phosphate battery</i>
<i>LIB</i>	<i>Lithium-ion battery</i>
<i>LMO</i>	<i>Lithium-ion Manganese Oxide battery</i>
<i>NMC</i>	<i>Nickel Manganese Cobalt oxide batteries</i>
<i>PHEV</i>	<i>Plug-in hybrid electric vehicle</i>

Introduction

MARBEL was born with the objective of filling the existing gap in the application of the principles of the circular economy (CE) in battery packs (BP), until now mostly conceptualized only under technical requirements (apart from a limited number of initiatives) and in order to support the automotive sector in its decarbonization.

This objective is based on the MARBEL-versatility (MV) axis defined in the proposal phase, which implies the development of an integrated solution that will cover the 4 CE (Circular Economy) categories defined by the European Commission (2020): Design and production, Use, Recovery and Support Value. Hence, ecodesign is probably the cross-cutting element that must always be present throughout the entire project, being the key step for miniaturized housing, the implementation of sustainable materials (recycled, recyclable, extruded and AI foam) and the arrangement of materials (topological optimization), plug-and-play capabilities, an improved cooling system, as well as innovative cellular wireless connections, among others. And all these aspects while providing the demonstrator with a reduced weight, with a longer useful life and a better performance mainly in energy density. This approach must support the primary goal of exceeding the planned goal of achieving a minimum 40% improvement in Life Cycle Assessment by adopting all the above improvements. All of them focused on the simultaneous reduction of both environmental impact and external costs, maximizing benefits and increasing the value of the product.

To this end, the entire consortium has been engaged on an ambitious collaborative common taskforce aimed at building a common scheme based on the study of environmental and technological requirements and by including improvement actions in the form of a set of generic strategies and concrete actions of ecodesign. All of this to be deployed during the execution of the project from the aforementioned circular perspective.

For this, the effective work framed in T2.5 has focused on a benchmarking of alternatives previously accounted for in a state of the art carried out within the framework of WP8, which in turn, has allowed to lay the foundations for environmental validation and evaluation with studies LCA and LCC that come to demonstrate the inherent benefits of MARBEL.

Thanks to that, enabling circular economy strategies through greater resource efficiency, modularity, easy disassembly, and repair with the use of potentially reusable materials and the replacement of virgin materials with secondary raw materials and by-products will result in significant savings on the global net resources.

The conceptualized preliminary design of the battery, which is the main result of the work carried out in WP2 and T2.5, is proposed with the objective of achieving all these objectives and has been reflected in section 3 of this deliverable. Not surprisingly, it is one of the main results of the work carried out in WP2, focused on the establishment of the requirements and guidelines for the development of the new BP concept and the definition of a preliminary conceptualization. As an open repository, everything published here will support the project and will make it possible to reinforce dissemination to all relevant actors in the sector's value chain during and after the project.

1. Hotspot's analysis of batteries for electric vehicles

This section presents a list of the most relevant issues related to the environmental performance of LIB batteries in electric vehicles. These issues (or hotspots) can affect to the entire life cycle of the battery, including the elements that interact with the battery and ensure its proper operation, such as the control modules and BMS. These hotspots are analysed in the next sections to determine the potential environmental impacts associated to each of them and determine the most appropriate strategies to approach each of them.

The compendium of the most relevant issues and hotspots is the result of the state-of-the-art included in deliverable 8.1. Main findings have been already discussed in such deliverable, summarizing in this report the ones with the greatest environmental impacts. This work has been addressed with the aim to evaluate a sort of different materials and designs following the Ecodesign principles in upcoming project steps according to strategies proposed and defined in Section 2. The hotspots have been organized following the life cycle stages of the battery system:

- 1) The raw materials extraction and components/battery manufacturing
- 2) The onboard use phase (in the vehicle)
- 3) The second life of the battery
- 4) The end of life of the battery and its waste management and potential recycling.

Figure 1. Life Cycle of MARBEL project. System boundaries for battery production (images: Flaticon.com'. These covers have been designed using resources from Flaticon.com)

Hotspots and main issues are detailed through different files, one for each stage analysed, where are reflected an impact range, which as an average, reflects the importance of the analysed stage in the whole life cycle. It is only a tentative indicator, based in the results released around different studies recovered and reflected in the “references” subsection.

RAW MATERIALS EXTRACTION AND COMPONENTS MANUFACTURING

**IMPACT
RANGE**

30% - 50%

HOTSPOTS & MAIN ISSUES

The contribution coming from the **production of structural parts (steel)** (Message et al)

Presence of metals on the **wiring System (copper)**, and their upstream extraction process (Message et al)

Regarding GWP, **EV as a whole and the battery mainly**, achieve higher impacts in relation to conventional vehicles (Hawkings et al)

The contribution coming from the **production of structural parts (Aluminium)** (Rinne et al)

Relevant metals like nickel, cobalt, lithium, and manganese are **toxic**, but allow to increase higher energy densities (Xion shu et al)

Regarding GWP, **Battery Management System** and energy demand (Fan et al)

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ON BOARD USE

IMPACT RANGE

50% - 80%

HOTSPOTS & MAIN ISSUES

Energy consumption is directly related to weight (Del Pero et al.)	The environmental performance of EVs relies on electricity mix in the same way than it does on energy use and vehicle lifetime (Hawkings et al)	Vehicle lifetime is governed by use and has a very important effect on whole EV life cycle (Hawkings et al)	Battery weight has as well effects in other important aspects, such as tyre and brake abrasion (Messagie et al)	Increasing the internal battery efficiency implies a reduction on the impact of the internal efficiency losses of the battery (Zackrisson et al.)
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SECOND LIFE

IMPACT RANGE

10% - 20%

HOTSPOTS & MAIN ISSUES

Peak shaving application of batteries (e.g., for a residential dwelling) entails environmental benefits thanks to avoiding battery manufacturing efforts (Bobba et al. (1))

Replacing a fresh LMO battery by a repurposed EV battery can improve up to 93%, mainly on production stages (Bobba et al. (2)).

There is a significant environmental benefit coming from involving EV batteries for second life application, despite their lower performance (Lokimidis et al).

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END OF LIFE

IMPACT RANGE

15% - 20%

HOTSPOTS & MAIN ISSUES

Battery recycling allows to decrease impacts due to Li and Co recovery (Messagie et al.)

A high collection rate is important to perform an effective recycling thus reducing the total battery impact (Nordelöf et al.)

The recovery of products counterbalances the drawbacks associated to an increase in energy consumption due to these operations (Aichberger et al)

The recycling of the cathode material is the main point related to improve environmental performance

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2. The Ecodesign approach. From strategies to actions

Material and design solutions in the MARBEL’s framework project implementation will be developed under an eco-design perspective. Ecodesign considers the integration of multiple aspects which stem from environmental, social, and economic motivations targeting a sustainable product in the early stages of design. This approach considers the entire life cycle of the product, not only the in-use phase also the manufacturing and end of life phases which are evaluated in terms of, among other aspects, energy and resource consumption.

In the automotive industry, such approach must deal with numerous influencing areas which lead to a complex process as the vehicle can be considered as a configuration of multiple components. For electrification purposes, many previous studies have been dedicated for similar objectives, as the study held by Schwartz et al (2016) aimed to improve a lithium-ion battery meanwhile reduce the costs while increasing the energy efficiency and the mass producibility. Or the study developed by PE INTERNATIONAL within ELIBAMA project, which through the integration of eco-design (ISO 14062) and LCA standards (ISO 14044) have been developed an eco-design tool.

On MARBEL, a similar approach is being addressed but having into account a cooperative well-defined perspective where all the partners had the chance to give feedback in the development and proposal of the different strategies conceptualized at the very beginning. Coupled to this, the definition of concrete eco-design actions was one of the most prominent pillars, which will reflect the planned work to be held along the 3,5 years of the project. With that view, multidisciplinary team lead by EURECAT and IREC have allowed to assure a common approach aligned with all WP technical development. The common objective will be to always consider a Life Cycle Perspective during project execution. The eco-design methodology has been defined following four key different stages:

Figure 2. Ecodesign framework under MARBEL project

STEP 1: Identification of Hotspots and Life Cycle Stages. After a detailed state of the art performed in the framework of WP8 and task 8.1, an assessment of conventional technologies, and for the three architectures (BEVs, HEVs and PHEVs), have allowed to determine a preliminary benchmark assessment to elucidate main aspects and stages with higher impact. Results are reflected in the section 1 of this deliverable.

STEP 2. Establishment of the most properly eco-design strategies based on STEP 1. Considering the results stated in stage 1, it has been investigated from those already available

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(e.g., lifetime extension, avoiding use of toxic materials, better energy efficiency on the battery architecture, etc.) which are the most promising strategies to be adopted case by case.

STEP 3. Alignment of technological procedures to the selected strategies. From the basis of the selected design strategies, it was suggested all necessary changes which will allow to minimize the use of resources and bring sustainability perception to all decisions made during the design process. To that respect, a workshop conducted by the leaders with the support of MIRO platform and the feedback of all attendants.

STEP 4. Selection of concrete eco-design actions and Battery Conceptualized Design. The final step is to have a battery concept design. This concept will gather all the information collected in this deliverable, regarding environmental perspectives, and the information from the rest of deliverables of WP2. For example, some of the eco-design strategies will be the Design for Assembly (DfA) and Modularity (DfM). Therefore, the concept battery will be the starting point for the designing in detail that, supported by the LCA, will iterate until get an eco-designed battery that achieve the environmental objectives of the project.

2.1 General ecodesign strategies.

Following the ecodesign framework proposed under MARBEL project, after the identification of the main issues and hotspots, the main strategies to tackle each of them is presented (step 2).

MARBEL partners have been discussing and prioritizing the most effective strategies that aim at tackling each of the hotspots that have been identified. At the end, 14 strategies have been selected and are presented as follows. For each strategy, their implication in each life cycle stage and potential environmental and cost benefits have been identified. Furthermore, for each strategy, a discussion on the innovative challenges for MARBEL's activity is included, to guide and support the actions that will be undertaken during the project.

STRATEGY 1
Effective material usage: lightweighting
LIFE CYCLE STAGE

Raw Materials extraction and components manufacturing

On board Use

Second Life

End of Life

ON STAGE IMPLICATIONS
HIGH
HIGH
MEDIUM
LOW
ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

Decrease in the use of natural resources

 Energy use minimization
Reduction potential of CO2 eq emissions

 Energy use minimization
Reduction potential of CO2 eq emissions potential

Less waste, less material and energy intensity

COST BENEFITS

Less material use implies less cost of components acquisition

Decreasing the intensity of electricity means less energy purchase

Extend battery life minimize the necessity of new storage systems

Costs for components valorisation are lower thanks to an extended amortization

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Lightweighting is beneficial in designing BEVs as it allows a higher range of energy density for the same cost, or similarly, a smaller battery and motor at constant range and performance. According to the study performed by Lux Research "Electric Vehicle Lightweighting 2030" Lightweighting must cost less than increase BEV range. Otherwise, it will make more economic sense to simply increase pack size. While there is some variation, the cost of lightweighting in 2030 must be less than \$5 per kilogram saved on average.

INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES

As stated by Luk et al (2010), the production of lightweight materials is often more GHG-intensive than the production of conventional materials, which leads to higher vehicle cycle (production) emissions. Therefore, the full life cycle needs to be considered to assess the GHG emission benefits of vehicle lightweighting. At the same time, the lightweight material used and its material substitution ratio (mass of lightweight material required to replace a unit mass of conventional material) must be clearly evaluated to do not obtain biased conclusions.

CONCLUSIONS

The impact of lightweighting on electric vehicles and consequently, on one of the heaviest parts as batteries depends on whether the battery is downsized to maintain driving range, which reduces both vehicle and fuel cycle GHG emissions. This is extremely important to assure the effectiveness of the strategy.

STRATEGY 2

Effective material usage: nature (type of material)

LIFE CYCLE STAGE

Raw Materials extraction and components manufacturing

On board Use

Second Life

End of Life

ON STAGE IMPLICATIONS

HIGH

NONE

NONE

LOW

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

Lower energy intensity in manufacturing
Decrease range of toxicity elements.

Preferable use of non-hybrid materials and well-established recyclable materials

COST BENEFITS

As a rule, recycled materials are cheaper

Simple recovery processes imply cost reduction and improved performance

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Lightweighting is a key strategy to cut-off impact of electric vehicles. However, the nature of the great range of materials currently in use needs to be highlighted. The **avoidance of CRMs in alloys**, the **use of recyclable materials** or **low intensity energy manufacturing options** must be stated in a conjunctive way.

INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES

The material used depends on its characteristics and the requirements of the application. For example, one material may offer superior stiffness while another is more malleable. The **materials** under consideration **could offer a significant weight advantage but impact from their production could increase their negative implications** in other impact vectors, which must be analysed.

CONCLUSIONS

Any strategy adopted to replace or introduce a new material must consider its nature. Sometimes design strategies focus on weight reduction. However, it is essential to analyse the material in a broader approach. The limitations regarding the use of **hybrid materials for their end of life**, the **necessary avoidance of resources with high levels of scarcity and / or the toxicity implementations of advanced materials should address any option in a context where the circular economy is gaining more and more importance**. Hence, materials substitution efforts need to pursue a reduction of overall lifecycle emissions, not just to make cars lighter which only affects the use-phase in the lifecycle.

STRATEGY 3

Enhancing smart charging options

LIFE CYCLE STAGE

ON STAGE IMPLICATIONS

NONE

HIGH

HIGH

NONE

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

Energy use minimization
Reduction potential of CO2 eq emissions

Energy use minimization
Reduction potential of CO2 eq emissions

COST BENEFITS

Decreasing the intensity of electricity means less energy to be purchased.

Extend the battery life minimizes the necessity of new storage systems.

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

According to ISO 15118, vehicle-to-grid communication for smart charging provides for data communication controls for the **integration of renewable energy in a charging session by enabling the variation and shifting of charging loads dependent on the electricity mix**. Therefore, charging stations are, in the case of high **shares of renewables and potential low electricity prices**, able to increase their load, support the feed-in of renewable energy and consequently, decreasing the environmental impact associated to energy acquisition with lower renewables ranges. And this, could be **complemented with a general strategy where the charging time could be reduced**, increasing the effectiveness in the adoption of these more beneficial periods where mix is determined with a higher rate in renewables.

INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES

BEVs require 6 - 12h for 80% battery charge. This situation could be solved by performing a set fast charges during the vehicle life, but manufacturers do not guarantee long-lasting reliability of the battery-pack. **Harsh and short thermal stresses due to fast charging are the most common limitations**. In that sense, **inaccurate cell voltage measure has the risk to produce overvoltage failures** during vehicle charge. Thus, ultra-fast charge requires of ultrafast and accurate methods of cell voltage measure to increase its efficiency

CONCLUSIONS

Electric vehicles can contribute to the electricity grid in two significant parts: **Along its lifetime on vehicle and for second-life options**. A flexible electricity demand by charging at the right time enabling hours with a higher renewable production is key and minimize the need for peak fossil plants. Smart charging including V2G in a potential second life represent an efficient use of resources.

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STRATEGY 4

Improve monitoring and state of cell and their capacity

LIFE CYCLE STAGE

ON STAGE IMPLICATIONS

LOW

HIGH

HIGH

NONE

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

Energy savings while driving

Reduce the number of tests to be carried out to find out the status of battery to decide the most suitable second life application.

COST BENEFITS

Energy saved and potential elongation of the lifespan of the battery to allow 1 replacement /300000 km.

Reduce the costs associated to determine the SoH of potential batteries candidates for second life.

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

This strategy aims at achieving a comprehensive information on the status of the battery by analysing the status of each cell. This information can be collected by the BMS that should be capable to use this information to act accordingly to use the cells that are in better conditions, identify which cells have degraded and calculate the current capacity of the battery. This information should be available by downloading the data sets by any battery operator System.

INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES

Define an algorithm for the BMS capable to extract the information of each cell and decide the operational use to maximise the efficiency and/or lifespan of the battery. The BMS shall also be capable to collect and prepare this information to be provided once the battery ends its first life in the vehicle.

CONCLUSIONS

Constant monitoring and accessibility to data on the status of the battery and cells provides information that will support choices to reduce the energy during the driving and to check applications for second life.

STRATEGY 5

Optimization of the driving conditions

LIFE CYCLE STAGE

ON STAGE IMPLICATIONS

NONE

HIGH

LOW

NONE

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

Energy consumption reduction, emission reduction, elongating the time from charge to charge, optimization of number of available cycles and an energy storage capacity elongation.

The battery arrives to a second life with a small reduction of its efficiency.

COST BENEFITS

Operational costs due to energy consumption reduction

Enlarge the type of applications where this battery can be used in second life: increase the amortization.

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

This strategy aims at reducing the energy consumed during the driving if different driving profiles are loaded into the BMS in order to maximise the efficiency of the battery for each scenario.

INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES

Are different profiles available to define different driving conditions scenarios? Vehicle and driving parameters should be used to perform optimized models of use phase and driving. Is the battery “fast enough” to adequate its energy release following the BMS instructions?

CONCLUSIONS

This strategy aims at reducing the energy consumed during the driving if different driving profiles are loaded into the BMS in order to maximise the efficiency of the battery for each scenario

STRATEGY 6

Enhancing of the battery efficiency

LIFE CYCLE STAGE

Raw Materials extraction and components manufacturing

On board Use

Second Life

End of Life

ON STAGE IMPLICATIONS

MEDIUM HIGH MEDIUM NONE

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS	Highly efficient materials in the cells: search for high density materials with lower environmental impact	Energy consumption reduction, elongating the time from charge to charge.	The battery arrives to a second life with a small reduction of its efficiency.
COST BENEFITS	Cost reduction due to the use of highly efficient materials, with lower mass and volume	Operational costs due to energy consumption reduction	Enlarge the type of applications where this battery can be used in second life: increase the amortization.

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

This strategy aims at improving the battery efficiency and reduce the slope for its degradation, elongating its lifespan to achieve the 300000 km that have been set as an objective with and SoH higher than 70-60% of SoH.

INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES

This strategy implies an efficient chemistry choice and improvement of the BMS design and performance. The use of methods to enhance the efficiency and life of battery, such as nanotechnology in lithium-ion (Li-ion) battery, configuration of parallel battery, battery charging and super-capacitors.

CONCLUSIONS

Check if this strategy can be analysed within the scope of MARBEL project, and to which extent. Flexible BMS design.

STRATEGY 7

Promotion of the second life from initial design

LIFE CYCLE STAGE

Raw Materials extraction and components manufacturing

On board Use

Second Life

End of Life

ON STAGE IMPLICATIONS

MEDIUM

LOW

HIGH

MEDIUM

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

Optimize the materials choice. Alleviate the use of virgin materials. "To dilute" the carbon footprint impact of the production stage through an elongating useful life of battery.

The design should not imply variations in the environmental behaviour during the driving.

Reduce the time and energy to disassemble the battery for a second life, Minimize the magnitude and pace of waste generation while at the same time reducing life cycle environmental impacts of energy systems.

Increase the share of materials that are can be recovered. Reduce the waste.

COST BENEFITS

Reduction in the consumption the materials

The design should not imply variations in the operational costs during the driving.

Cost reduction due to less consumption of human resources and energy to conditionate the battery for a second life

To be checked as it will depend on the cost of the recycling and the value of the materials that can be recovered.

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Thinking the battery for its first life in the vehicle and its potential second life, in different configurations: stacked, whole battery, modules, cells levels. End of life should be considered as some cells might not be suitable for second life and therefore should be treated for recovery.

INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES

Optimize the design to minimize overall environmental impacts for both first and second life: robust, light, and long-lasting (first life), easy to disassemble and modular for second life. Avoid the use of glues for battery case (use screws instead). The whole battery or battery module must be adapted to the new energy storage device including the cooling possibilities and battery management system.

CONCLUSIONS

This strategy aims at focusing on the initial design of the battery to maximize, together, the environmental and economic impacts of both first and second life. Promotion of the use of recycled and recyclable materials, improve the modularity, avoid composites should be considered to achieve this goal

STRATEGY 8

Design for EoL (End of life)

LIFE CYCLE STAGE				
	Raw Materials extraction and components manufacturing	On board Use	Second Life	End of Life
ON STAGE IMPLICATIONS	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	LOW
ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS	Optimize the materials choice.	The design should not imply variations in the environmental behaviour during the driving.	Reduce the time and energy to disassemble the battery for a second life, waste reduction.	Increase the share of materials that are can be recovered. Reduce the waste.
COST BENEFITS	Reduction in the consumption the materials	The design should not imply variations in the operational costs during the driving.	Cost reduction due to less consumption of human resources and energy to conditionate the battery for a second life	Check the cost of the recycling of the materials and balance it to the cost of secondary materials.

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Recyclability of a battery should be considered at the design stage by using naturally abundant resources and recyclable battery technologies. The recycling of end-of-life batteries not only minimizes the demand for critical material resources but also addresses significant concerns regarding environmental pollution and ecological impacts. Additionally, it is a special critical issue, where balancing supply of lithium with future demand is a critical challenge in EU. **Cascade effect by the recovery of lithium, aluminium, and copper could reduce the energy intensity of battery production by approximately 40% to 50%.**

INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES

Nowadays LIBs are recycled through **pyrometallurgical processes, or hydrometallurgical processes coupled to a crushing pre-treatment stage.** Both options with a **huge economic and environmental impact.** However, the current LIB design hinders the use of more economic and environmental options, like **cell dismantling and cathode-specific hydrometallurgical processes.** First, the **lack of compositional labelling for easy identification,** is a barrier to more nuanced recycling schemes. Most battery packs contain no information about the chemistry used meaning that cells from the different packs need to be dealt with by the same process (Pyro or Crushing). Improved battery labelling would enable different battery chemistries to be separated before processing and would prevent contamination between e.g., NMC and LFP chemistries. Secondly, **facilitate the automation of the battery packs dismantling (solid bars instead of flexible cables, avoid the use of binders or weldings, standardisation of bolts and tools, etc)** are other improvements examples. Additionally, access to cell components, should be improved, especially regarding the selection of binders (**binders that can be dispersed with aqueous solutions**)

CONCLUSIONS

This strategy aims at focusing on the initial design of the battery to maximize, together, the environmental and economic impacts of both first and second life. Promotion of the use of recycled and recyclable materials, improve the modularity, avoid composites should be taken into account to achieve this goal.

STRATEGY 9

General structure optimization

LIFE CYCLE STAGE

ON STAGE IMPLICATIONS

HIGH

HIGH

HIGH

LOW

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

Decrease in the use of natural resources.

Energy use minimization
Reduction potential of CO2 eq emissions

Energy use minimization
Reduction potential of CO2 eq emissions

Less waste, less material and energy intensity

COST BENEFITS

Less material use implies less cost of components acquisition.

Decreasing the intensity of electricity means less energy purchase.

Extend battery life minimize the necessity of new storage systems.

Costs for components valorisation are lower thanks to an extended amortization.

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Many often it is found the situation that **improving the overall performance of the design can result in the addition of mass** which could offset the beneficial effects. An **optimal structure must be able to reduce the mass and volume of the battery by eliminating parasitic components** of the functional structure, such as structural "**overpacking**". In that sense, the **relocation of cells in the structure is beneficial in most cases, even using a simple design process.**

INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES

The **FEA method** is commonly used to simulate and predict the **behaviour of a battery**. These models have been successfully applied showing that **optimal redistribution of battery mass and removal of its parasitic mass can reduce stress on frame components and overall deformation** when subjected to simulated launch vibrations.

CONCLUSIONS

To **reduce volume** of battery could implies two well defined benefits. First, due to a **reduction in total weight**, which allow to **optimize energy** consumption during use phase. Secondly, thanks to opportunity created to **increase battery energy density, allowing the introduction of more cells extending battery capacity.**

STRATEGY 10

Promote a design to allow repairing and refurbishment to enable reuse

LIFE CYCLE STAGE

Raw Materials extraction and components manufacturing

On board Use

Second Life

End of Life

ON STAGE IMPLICATIONS

LOW

NONE

HIGH

LOW

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

Optimize the materials choice.

N/A

Reduce the time and energy to disassemble the battery for a second life or material's valorisation.

Increase the share of materials that can be recovered. Reduce the waste generated.

COST BENEFITS

Reduction in the consumption of materials

N/A

Cost reduction due to less consumption of human resources and energy to conditionate the battery for a second life or material's valorisation

Check the cost of the recycling of the materials and balance it to the cost of secondary materials.

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Considering the emerging LIB deployment for EVs, a well-defined and proactive EOL far away from conventional "take use & disposal" strategies is needed. Circular economy (CE) principles such as reuse, and recycling are mandatory. In this context, a circular or closed-loop economy aims to **eliminate waste by cycling materials and products within the system to achieve better resource and energy efficiency as well as profitability**. Both reuse and recycling enhanced by a well and defined **repair and refurbishment operations** allow to **avoid primary materials production and reducing disposal of potentially hazardous elements**.

INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES

The **difficulty of separating parts of the products limits the development of repair, upgrade, and remanufacture specific operations**. By analysing the removal of battery packs to be used in newer applications or directly, prior to be completely separated in valuable materials, is more than necessary. For that reason, an effective design must account potential benefits and drawbacks. Disassembly tasks for removal of batteries must be highlighted and available for all stakeholders involved.

CONCLUSIONS

Disassembly can be a quite time and cost consuming process and hence must be planned properly. A planning approach for the needed operations must be considered not only for the EoL operations, but for second life purposes as well.

2.2 Ecodesign actions

All the ecodesign strategies defined and presented in the previous section would be meaningless if they were only presented as "big headlines" of the improvements to be made in the design of the batteries and their viability was not determined from a technical point of view. In fact, the technical aspect must always be present since it is and must be the main limiting factor when it comes to materializing or not.

With this idea on the horizon, a workshop was developed in which the different technological agents had the opportunity to explore the potential of each of the strategies and exchange their impressions about their convenience. Through the MIRO platform, it was possible to specify much more each of these strategies and to be able to specify them in concrete actions to be carried out in the project.

And it is that beyond the fact that everything that will be developed in MARBEL is well defined from a technical point of view, it is unavoidable that all technological agents work together towards a common objective, which is to reduce the impact of the battery developed with respect to what which is currently available on the market. In addition, this workshop allowed all those developers to start considering the environmental variable from the initial design stage, a fundamental pillar of the application of ecodesign.

Figure 3. Screenshot of the MIRO board completed during the workshop.

At the end, all different feedback provided ended with an internal discussion about the most prominent ecodesign actions to be developed along project implementation which will be into accounted in the conceptualization of the battery design. List of them is provided below:

Action 1: Use of recycled and recyclable materials, for example, in the extrusion of Aluminium profiles.

Action 2: Reduction of copper material needed for electronic components (cables, wirings, etc.)

Action 3: Adopt a "design for reuse, dismantling and recycling" approach by using easy recoverable and recyclable materials instead hybrid ones.

Action 4: Topological optimization of profiles to be used in the BP housing. This simulation will calculate the minimum material necessary to comply with the mechanical requirements.

Action 5: Reduce the quantities of soldering parts of the battery to minimize use of resources and facilitate end of use and second life operations.

Action 6: Use joining elements that can easily be removed to facilitate disassembly, as screws instead of glues to seal the battery pack /modules case.

Action 7: To define and include a protocol for the disassembly operations to assure safety conditions.

Action 8: Introduce a weldless connection to the cells to support disassembly, repairing, etc, options.

Action 9: Reduce whole weight of the battery by using lightweight materials in the casing elements (Al, Mg alloys,) and by choosing a high gravimetric energy chemistry in the electrodes composition that reduces the mass and keeps the energy capacity of the battery.

Action 10: An enhanced BMS that provides advanced degradation rate estimations to optimize battery usage in terms of an extended lifespan.

Action 11: Design a BMS with a multipurpose approach for both primary and second life options of the battery.

Action 12: To create a cloud connecting environment where data associated to the battery could be downloaded at any time during its lifetime and 2nd life extension.

Action 13: Develop a BMS able to respond second life applications by connecting to 200 modules.

Action 14: Adopt a battery pack design able to be easily repaired, refurbished, and reused with limited interventions.

3. Conceptualized battery design

The information provided in the previous section will be used to provide an initial concept design of the battery. This concept will list the main parts of the battery (profiles, BMS, thermal management system, charging system, module case, housing case, etc).

This information will be used for the development of WP5 tasks and to perform the economic, environmental and second life tasks in WP8. In fact, the LCA that will be performed in WP8 will help to complete the analyses of the battery and support the design of the configuration of the battery considering the materials, assembly, disassembly, and recyclability guidelines.

There are several problems from an environmental point of view in the batteries currently available within the market.

- The batteries are designed as a single use. After their life cycle, they are disposal even though there are still too many parts and materials with value.
- The baseplate is usually welded to the structural profiles while the cover plate is sealed to them, that make it very difficult to disassemble.
- All be electrical connection are wired.
- The whole shape of the battery is adapted to the current car structures which lead to a non-optimized use of materials and oversized parts.
- The connections between cells are welded, making almost impossible to disassemble them.
- For the cooling system, it is common to use thermal pastes that can't be recycled.
- The chemistry of the cells is out of the scope of this project. However, the difficulty on dismantling the modules make impossible to properly recycle the lithium.
- The use of composite materials is also a recyclability problem.
- The batteries are not design for a second life use, so the parts are disposal instead of reused or recycled.

Considering the main requirements from the previous section and the other deliverables from WP2 and the problem with the current batteries, the next step is to conceptualize the design of

the battery. The following pictures are just a concept to understand the ecodesign actions considered, the final battery pack will be different.

Profile's structure

One of the main components of a battery pack is the structural part. This part is usually made by profiles. Within the Marbel project, these profiles will be extruded. The alloy selected could vary, but the first options is to use the 6063. This alloy is easily recyclable and can be recycled. The main objective is to use a maximum of 50% of the alloy recycled. The final percentage of the recycled material will be determined after the characterization of the profiles within task 5.2 and task 5.4 from the WP5.

Figure 4. Concept of the battery housing profiles.

Regarding the welding perspective, the goal is to have the minimum parts welded. Nevertheless, because of the structural requirements, there are parts such as the corners that must be welded.

The geometry of the profiles will be also optimized by using simulation software. This kind of tools will provide a geometry with the minimum material possible able to hold all the loads and efforts.

Baseplate

The baseplate is the bottom cover of the battery pack. This component is usually welded to the profiles. One of the main problems from an environmental point of view is that these covers are usually manufactured with a different material than the profiles. This aspect is a problem for the welding and for the recyclability of the battery.

Figure 5. Baseplate of the battery pack.

Therefore, for the Marbel battery pack, it will be tried to be without welding or at least with the minimum welded joints.

Modules

The following picture shows the structure of the module placed in the housing. Each module will be easy to assembly and disassembly which will help to repair them if there are any damage or to reassemble in case of a second life applications. The materials used for the housing structure of the modules will be also recyclable and recycled if possible. A study of using the same material than the battery pack will be done since will be beneficial from and recycling point of view.

Figure 6. Concept of the modules

Cells

As the modules, they will be easily placed and removable and connected without welding. This ecodesign action will help with the second life application, the recyclability of the cells and to repair it if needed.

Figure 7. Concept layout of the cells and modules placed in the battery pack.

Other components

The rest of the components as the BMS, the cooling system or the fixation ones for example, will be also considered from an environmental point of view. The connection between the BMS and

the cells will be wireless. An average of the total weight of these components from other batteries will be considered to reduce the total weight for them in the Marbel battery pack.

Figure 8. Concept layout for the rest of the components.

The screws, nuts, washer and so on will be calculated to reduce the number of them without affecting the performance. There are also possibilities to use different materials, that will be studied considering the environmental perspective.

There are different options that will be analysed for the thermal management in WP3. A balance between the performance and the environmental aspect will be consider for deciding the final option.

Aluminium foam	Vapor chamber	Heating pad
Foam that increases the heat transfer and the mechanical properties.	Thin and lightweight vapours chamber inserted between cells	Foil heaters that provide reliable heat source for EV battery pack

Table 1. Different option for the cooling system

Cover plate

Finally, the cover plate. The purpose is to use the same material (6063 Aluminium) than the profiles that will also help with the recyclability. In this case, the plate will be bolted so it will be easy to assembly, reassembly or reused for a second application. One of the challenges will be the tightness of the whole structure (because it will be screw and not welded or seal).

Figure 9. Cover plate

4. Conclusions

All the work done has allowed:

Determine the most relevant issues related to the environmental performance of LIB batteries in electric vehicles to determine the basis of the most appropriate strategies to address each of them. Aspects related to the production of structural parts with specific materials such as CRM and others such as nickel, cobalt, lithium and manganese in their manufacture, the importance of weight and the electrical mix used as well as the useful life of the vehicle during use, as well as the saving. they come from the replacement of the new LMO battery with a reused EV battery in the second life and finally the related importance of recovering valuable elements such as Li and Co to reduce the impact at the end of the useful life.

Define a methodological approach to ecodesign, which under a collaborative framework, has made it possible to define a set of 10 generic ecodesign strategies aimed at covering all these hotspots and stages of the life cycle of the battery itself. And added to that, under this same collaborative approach, it has been able to carry out 14 ecodesign actions that technology providers consider during their technical work throughout the project and that will be evaluated to end up being implemented in the final design.

And finally, **provide an initial concept design of the battery** that considers the main parts of the battery (profiles, BMS, thermal management system, charging system, module box, housing box, etc.) and the main requirements deployed throughout WP2.

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